

PRESS RELEASE | APRIL 2024

UNICA4EU Project Successfully Concludes: Pioneering AI Solutions for Childhood Cancer

The UNICA4EU project, a pioneering initiative aimed at leveraging Artificial Intelligence (AI) to combat childhood cancer in Europe, proudly announces the successful completion of its joint endeavour, supported by the European Commission. Childhood cancer remains a pressing health challenge, with approximately 35,000 new cases diagnosed annually in Europe. Recognizing the urgent need for innovative approaches, the UNICA4EU project has diligently worked towards setting the fundamentals to address data scarcity and fragmentation in paediatric oncology.

Over the course of its tenure, UNICA4EU has galvanized a collaborative effort among 15 partners across 8 European countries, including prominent organisations such as SIOP Europe and CCI Europe. Together, the consortium has laid the groundwork for a robust European Paediatric Cancer ecosystem, with a vision to revolutionize cancer care while upholding patient welfare and data protection.

Highlighting Key Achievements

Multi-disciplinary standards of care supported by Artificial Intelligence

Focused on harnessing the potential of AI in paediatric oncology while respecting standards and ethics, the UNICA4EU project has underscored the importance of leveraging diverse data sources to enhance diagnostic and therapeutic approaches. Emphasizing adherence to regulatory guidelines and best practices, our work has highlighted the critical need for comprehensive guidance in implementing AI in healthcare. Through tangible use cases and multidisciplinary cooperation, we have addressed challenges in data preparation, AI implementation, and regulatory frameworks.

UNICA4EU's Knowledge Base

A cornerstone in the project's trajectory, we have laid the foundation for AI application in paediatric cancer by creating a comprehensive framework. Through extensive surveys and focus group discussions, insights were gleaned to guide the project's multidisciplinary approach towards the definition of governance structures for data sharing, ownership, and protection. The establishment of our [Knowledge Base](#), featuring decision trees for AI development, key resources and references to critical cross-over –ethical, regulatory, legal and social– topics, further bolstered efforts to standardize data collection and leverage AI for paediatric cancer research.

Synergies with ongoing communities, outreach and exploitation

Dedicated to community building for paediatric haemato-oncology, UNICA4EU has successfully fostered collaboration and knowledge exchange among stakeholders, strengthening the foundation for future initiatives in the field.

As the UNICA4EU project draws to a close, it leaves behind a legacy of collaboration, innovation, and hope in the fight against childhood cancer. All these efforts will culminate in the upcoming publication of a special edition of the [European Journal of Cancer – Paediatric Oncology](#), featuring a collection of white papers and manuscripts authored by UNICA4EU consortium partners.

Through tireless efforts and unwavering dedication, the consortium has propelled the European Paediatric Cancer ecosystem towards a future where AI-driven solutions hold the promise of transforming lives. Moving forward, we invite stakeholders and supporters to share our vision for a brand-new **European Childhood Cancer Data Initiative** and join us in our ongoing endeavors to combat childhood cancer and ensure a brighter, healthier future for our children.

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